

PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF RESUMPTION OF IN-PERSON CLASSES ON THE LEARNING ATTITUDES OF LABORATORY SCHOOL LEARNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 9

Pages: 927-937

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2017

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12699126

Manuscript Accepted: 06-03-2024

Phenomenological Study on the Impact of Resumption of In-person Classes on the Learning Attitudes of Laboratory School Learners

Princess Stephanie B. Rayray,* Cassandra Alexa T. Bagarra, Sandra Camille C. Bermudez,
Markko Enzo S. Galvez, Ma. Ydane G. Javier, Joseph A. Villarama
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Due to pandemic, Philippine education system experienced shifts in learning modalities. Reimplementation of full in-person classes received varying views and attitudes from students. Anchored on Nora and Crisp's Mentoring Theory, which involves importance of psychological and academic support in student learning and development, this study evaluated learning attitudes of laboratory high school students in terms of their learning challenges and coping mechanisms. A combination of Husserl's descriptive phenomenology and Heidegger's interpretive phenomenology described and interpreted the lived experiences of 12 laboratory school learners from Central Luzon State University, Philippines by which data were gathered through semi-structured interview and analyzed following Collaizi's Method. Results revealed that students are generally favorable towards in-person classes, while some are reluctant due to adjustments they had to undergo. Moreover, as in-person classes were normalized, students were found to have difficulty meeting the demands of face-to-face classes and experienced exhaustion. As response, students developed adaptive and maladaptive coping mechanisms. Findings serve as guide for educational institutions to reform the current education system taking into account the learning attitudes of students in developing effective teaching approaches and strategies.

Keywords: *laboratory school learners, in-person classes, learning attitudes, challenges, coping mechanisms*

Introduction

The coronavirus pandemic significantly influenced the Philippine education system as the learning setup had shifted from traditional to virtual. In line with various academic preparations, the Department of Education (DepEd) proposed initiatives in addressing educational difficulties brought by the pandemic (Bordeos et al., 2022). In accordance, most schools implemented online learning, either synchronous or asynchronous, for students to keep up with the learning process amid the pandemic. Students showed favor towards learning in an online classroom setup as they are in control of their own learning pace (Ejus & Juanis, 2020). However, students also view online learning at a low level due to restricted interaction and inaccessible technology (Nuangchalem et al., 2021).

As the world begins to adjust to the catastrophic effect of COVID-19, academic institutions shift from purely online to blended learning. Students' response on the implementation of blended learning were mostly disapproval due to their incapacities in acquiring resources, self-studying, and developing coping mechanisms (Lunesto et al., 2021).

As full face-to-face classes get gradually implemented, associated with are the varying views and attitudes of students while adjusting to a new learning modality. The Inter-Agency

Task Force has recently lowered the alert level status in the country, allowing workplaces to operate at 100% capacity provided that the public will follow the implemented protocols (PNA, 2022). Students are more prepared and supportive of face-to-face learning than flexible learning (Andal et al., 2022). Students who took in-person classes experienced a sense of belongingness with their peers (Chen et al., 2022).

The current research endeavor is in alignment with the theoretical model for mentoring (Nora & Crisp, 2007) which focuses on the factors that should be involved in the mentor-mentee relationship. This includes psychological support, career assessment, academic knowledge support, and role model presence, which are all crucial in student development. In this matter, the current research benefits educators and researchers in determining students' learning attitudes on the reimplementation of full in-person classes. Factors of academic mentoring are referred to identify students' learning challenges. Data gathered from this study provides insight on how academic institutions may cater their lapses and provide the needs of students during the transition towards a new learning system.

Research Objectives

In the hopes for educational institutions to develop teaching approaches and strategies that are molded to take account of the students' learning attitudes to provide quality education for students, this study evaluated the consequences of the resumption of full in-person classes on the learning attitudes of laboratory high school learners in terms of (1) challenges faced and (2) coping mechanisms developed.

Literature Review

Philippine Landscape on Academic Teaching and Learning Modalities

In the Philippines, education has been viewed on high regards as it serves as the cornerstone of progress and societal development. Over the years, the educational landscape in the country has undergone shifts and transformations, which were caused by historical events, colonial influences, and continuous reforms (Cimene et al., 2023). As per definition provided by the Cambridge dictionary, the word “landscape” usually refers to the appearance of a large area of land, but it could also refer to all the features of a situation. Consequently, the educational landscape does not solely concern the structural landscape of educational institutions but concerns all aspects in relation to it. Hence, the educational landscape also encompasses teaching and learning styles, attitudes, and principles.

In 2020, teaching and learning modality have abruptly shifted from traditional face-to-face learning into remote learning as COVID-19 pandemic prevailed globally (Borres et al., 2023). This initiative is in line with academic preparations done by the Department of Education (DepEd) in addressing educational difficulties brought by the pandemic (Bordeos et al., 2022). The outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic affected the lives of people worldwide. This mostly impacted the social physical connectivity of people due to emergency lockdowns and stay-at-home advisories implemented as a response to the threat posed by COVID-19 pandemic (O'Regan et al., 2021). With this response, numerous sectors, including educational sectors have been compromised resulting in immediate changes in teaching and learning modalities (i.e., virtual learning, distance learning). Although these changes in learning modalities were done in addressing educational difficulties amidst the pandemic, challenges like lack of social interactivity among students and teachers arises (Bali & Liu, 2018). Social interaction is said to be vital to the learning process of students. According to Hurst et al. (2013), students can learn more when they are able to be actively involved and talk with each other. They highlight that students viewed social interaction plays a vital role in honing their comprehension and retention skills via activating prior knowledge, making connections, and integrating new ideas. It also creates a positive environment for learning and working together, as well as enhancing their critical thinking and problem solving skills. Likewise, they also mentioned that teachers benefit from social interaction as it helps them in improving their teaching strategies and shaping them as an effective educator. Hence, abrupt changes in traditional learning modality still resulted in another educational difficulty: lack of social interactivity, which negatively affected both students and teachers. This lack of interactivity further resulted in changes in students' behavior, such as attention issues and difficulties in emotionally connecting to others (Copeland et al., 2021). Consequently, this may imply the lack of preparedness and poor planning of educational organizations (Babbar & Gupta, 2021) as such action occurred due to consequences of COVID-19 pandemic.

As restriction in COVID-19 pandemic has lifted, there have been another changes in learning modalities, from purely virtual learning into blended learning into reimplementation of full in-person learning. These changes reopen the opportunity for more social interactivity as both blended learning and full in-person learning enabled the students to have peer-to-peer interaction (Paul & Jefferson, 2019) and received immediate feedback from their advisers (Villarama et al., 2022). Additionally, this also makes collaborative activities easier and more manageable because of equal work distribution and better communication (Mather & Sarkans, 2018). However, above the benefits offered by gradual reimplementation of in-person learning, the situation most likely received opposing views and opinions from students, especially since they grew accustomed with virtual learning. With that, this research sought to investigate the attitudes and coping mechanisms of students as in-person classes are reimplemented.

Attitudes and Coping Mechanisms on Implementation of In-Person Classes

Attitude refers to the evaluation or views of oneself about a person, thing, place, or event. It can be positive or negative. Moreover, this can be resulted from an experience, social influence, or upbringing (George, 2021). The abrupt changes in learning modalities during the pandemic compelled students to study at home and enforced virtual learning. The earlier implementation of virtual learning received varying views from students. In the Philippines, students are reluctant to virtual learning due to technological and financial constraints (Baloran, 2020). A year later, students in Nairobi viewed online learning as a challenge due to technological difficulties resulting from lack of orientation to enhance their level of computer literacy (Ondicho, 2021). However, after a few years of studying at home and adapting to the home-based learning setup, the news of reimplementation of in-person classes resulted in varying views from students. In a recent study by Hoerunisa et al. (2022), they found that despite the difficulties (i.e., technological) posed by virtual learning, especially on its earlier implementation, students later on found it more comfortable and convenient as it gives them more freedom in terms of schedule and flexibility. Accordingly, Nikolopoulou (2022) reported the same sentiments from students where students expressed their fondness of the utilization of online instruction for conceptual courses. However, at the same time, she reported that students are more favorable in in-person classes for practical courses. In the similar year, the Philippines gradually implemented in-person classes via the implementation of blended learning. Bordeos et al. (2022) revealed that students who participated in blended classes expressed their dislikeness in blended learning as it is difficult for them to adjust again to this learning modality. Meanwhile, after a year, learners are becoming more interested in face-to-face classes as it lessens the restrictions (i.e., social interaction) posed by the pandemic.

Adjusting to different modalities posed difficulties and challenges, where students must cope in order to adapt to the learning modalities. Chowdhury (2019) explained that coping mechanisms vary from each individual. Students at the time of pandemic resorts to adaptive coping strategies like resource management and utilization, seeking learning assistance, and managing their learning environment (Del Rosario et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the later status of students during the virtual learning revealed that students end up employing

maladaptive coping strategies (e.g., drinking) in hopes to overcome the difficulties they faced during this virtual learning (Kgarose & Ramoshaba, 2022). With this, in the same year, Olleras et al. (2022) suggested that learners' readiness on modalities highly reflected teachers' performances and services. Additionally, Olleras et al. suggested that learners' readiness plays a vital role in how they will view learning and aspects in-relation with this (e.g., learning modalities). Hence, this study further sought to investigate the factors that affect students' attitudes on reimplementation of in-person classes.

Factors Affecting Students' Attitudes on Implementation of In-person Classes

Following the pandemic, students' attitudes are influenced by a number of factors when they return to in-person classes. These factors are mostly affected by their encounters with technology and altered lifestyles during remote learning.

Reasons that may affect learners' attitudes in a blended learning environment have been researched. With that being said, the familiarity and expertise that students have with technology significantly influence their attitudes towards e-learning. According to Aleksieva et al. (2018), students typically have positive views toward technology that they find comfortable using, indicating that having a strong technological foundation is essential to influencing their educational experiences. This suggests that students who are more proficient with digital tools have a more positive perception of e-learning, maybe because they are less frustrated and more efficient when using online platforms. This ability made the transition to remote learning environments easier.

Moreover, the views of students toward distant learning are greatly influenced by demographic factors, including gender, age, and employment. However, research on gender differences, which is one of the most well investigated factors, has shown different results. According to Birbal et al. (2018), there are notable gender-based disparities in attitudes, with male students typically exhibiting a more positive attitude toward blended learning than their female counterparts. This might be explained by the different degrees of comfort and confidence that the sexes have with technology. On the other hand, Ora et al. (2018) found no evidence of a significant gender difference, indicating that other factors, such as the blended learning program's unique design or the cultural context, may have a greater impact on these views than gender alone.

Another factor that has been looked into by researchers which may affect students' attitudes is prior learning experience with both online and blended learning. Although, it was identified that these had little impact on students' performance in blended courses (Asarta & Schmidt, 2020). Further, demographic factors, learning experiences, and computer literacy affect the students' learning attitudes, in which computer literacy is identified to be one of the most important components in observing blended learning (Sanpanich, 2020). However, given the return of traditional full in-person classes, factors such as computer literacy, which presumably played a crucial part in hybrid learning (Sanpanich, 2020), might only have little impact towards students' attitudes in traditional learning.

Additionally, students' lifestyles were drastically changed by the COVID-19 pandemic, which had an effect on their levels of physical activity and sleep patterns. Many students reported having extended sleep lengths and different sleep patterns during lockdowns, according to Ranjbar et al. (2021). While some may have benefited from this adjustment, others may have found it difficult to acclimate to the regimented timetables of traditional classroom settings. To add, according to Bermundo et al. (2019), students frequently experience sleep deprivation, which can have a detrimental effect on their mood and cognitive abilities. This could have an impact on their attitudes and performance in a traditional classroom setting.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers conduct a combination of Husserl's descriptive phenomenology, a phenomenological research approach in attaining a vivid and detailed description of the perceived lived experiences. Further, using Heidegger's interpretive phenomenology, a phenomenological research approach, guides the researchers in studying (analyzing and interpreting) the lived experiences (Heotis, 2020). In addition, the researchers of the study deal with the previous and present experiences and perceptions of the laboratory high school learners.

Participants

The research study adapted a "non-probability sampling technique," a purposeful sampling, that helps the researchers in choosing participants based on the researchers' knowledge and judgment (Fleetwood, 2022; Shaheen et al., 2019). This sampling technique was utilized as it helps the researchers in selecting participants that are qualified to provide answers needed to fulfill the objectives of the study. In this study, 12 laboratory high school learners, six (6) students from CLSU Science High School and six (6) students from Agricultural Science and Technology School (ASTS) assist the researchers in fulfilling their research objectives and purpose of the study. In the conduct of this undertaking, CLSU Science High School and ASTS learners are both in focus. The following criteria applies to select qualified participants in the study: (1) studying at a laboratory school particularly CLSU-USHS and ASTS; (2) experienced the transition from emergency remote learning to full face-to-face classes; (3) have agreed to voluntarily participate in the study. Furthermore, the researchers used codes in labeling and identifying the participants' statements: SU denotes that the students were from CLSU-USHS, and SA denotes that the students were from ASTS. The numbers beside the code indicate the grade level of the participants.

Instruments

For the profiling of each respondent, a checklist form asking for their personal information, such as biological sex, age, school, and grade level, was given to each of them.

Along with this is a copy of guide questions, approved by a professional, for a 10-minute semi-structured interview as a reference for each respondent.

Procedure

The researchers conduct a recorded one-on-one 10-minute semi-structured interview that tackles the laboratory high school learners' challenges and coping strategies. The interview was recorded as per permitted by the interviewee. Followed by utilizing "Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis" to analyze and interpret the data. Colaizzi's method of data analysis allowed the researchers to attain understanding and insights into experiences of laboratory school learners on resumption of in-person classes (Bakon et al., 2018). This method of data analysis encompasses seven stages (Applebaum et al., 2019) which significantly helped the researchers in analyzing and interpreting the collected data. The seven stages of data analysis include: (1) reading the transcript, (2) pulling out significant statements, (3) interpreting the statements, (4) grouping the drawn meanings into themes, (5) deriving descriptions based on the phenomenon, (6) reporting the phenomenon's importance, and (7) verifying the findings, to show emergent themes and its interwoven relationships, ensuring that none of the details of the phenomenon is overlooked. Accordingly, after the data have been analyzed and interpreted, the results have been communicated to the interviewee to validate the accuracy of interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

This research project adhered to the ethical standards as reviewed and approved by the Central Luzon State University Ethics Research Committee. Further, the study was given the CLSU-ERC approval code 2023-174 on March 14, 2023. Hence, upon receiving the ERC approval (code 2023-174), the researchers proceeded to conduct the study. The ERC and ethical participants of the study. Additionally, it provided the aims and objectives of the research study and it served as the guide of research design and protocols.

Results and Discussion

After a thorough conduct of series of semi-structured interviews with the participants and data cross-checking among six (6) experts, the following are three (3) emerging major themes having two (2) sub-themes each.

Attitudes of Students towards the Resumption of Full In-person Classes

Students showed contradicting reactions upon the announcement of the reimplementing of full face-to-face classes. After analysis, two sub-themes: excitement and unfamiliarity have emerged as the ruling attitudes shown by laboratory school learners.

Excitement

I was excited and ready to make friends din... Kasi 'yong lockdown po is very ano... Ang lonely niya po sa feeling. (SA8)

[I was excited and ready to make friends as well... because the lockdown imposed a sense of loneliness.] (SA8)

I felt happy because... because I get to see my friends often and I think classes are really fun. (SA7)

Lack of interaction during virtual learning immensely affected the social life of an 8th grade student and 7th grade student, who both are still at the early stage of the transition phase from elementary to high school.

Transitioning to a new learning environment requires many adjustments from students as it will be different from their previous learning environment. Especially since in this new learning environment, they can meet new faces who can be their friends and will associate with them for their remaining high school years.

Socializing with people during this transition is very vital for students as it can help them to fully adapt and adjust to the new environment. However, the pandemic restricted this social interaction as students were compelled to study at home via employing virtual classes. Hence, those students who were transitioning from elementary to high school during the pandemic were deprived of the privilege of meeting co-students who can be with them during this transition period and help them adapt to the new learning environment. With that, when in-person classes were announced to be reimplement, the same students from the transition period were excited about the news as it opens up the opportunity for them to finally meet people and make friends who may be with them throughout their highschool life.

Meanwhile, despite the excitement felt by a 10th grade student, this student can't help but to feel nervous about the experiences that in-person classes may bring.

Syempre po sobrang excited tapos kinakabahan... kasi this year I'm finally going to experience high school life. (SA10)

[Of course, I was excited, but nervous at the same time... because this year I'm finally going to experience high school life.] (SA10)

Being a high school student for the past three years during the pandemic where the education was continued virtually and within the comfort of their home, hearing the news of reimplementation of full in-person classes make these students feel both excited and nervous. Especially since this will be their first time meeting their classmates and teachers from their online classes and finally experiencing the high school life they have been anticipating since their virtual learning during their previous 7th, 8th, and 9th grade.

Online learning restricted students to interact with their peers despite it being an important aspect in learning (Gherhes et al., 2021). Learning in a traditional classroom setup is more preferred than virtual setup because of social interaction (Bali & Liu, 2018). Face-to-face interaction enhances learning among students in a way that visuospatial skills are made use of (Ransom et al., 2022). Socialization inside the classroom is essential in effective learning (Adnan & Anwar, 2020) especially when practical courses are involved. Moreover, Borres et al. (2023) found in their study that younger students showed readiness towards limited face-to-face classes because of their first time experiencing a high school environment.

Unfamiliarity

On the other hand, beyond the excitement of students, some still displayed a reluctant attitude, particularly the sense of unfamiliarity that they felt during the re-implementation of full in-person classes. As quoted below:

[Nangibabaw po 'yung] kaba kasi andun yung sense na maninibago ako na gagawa ako ng maraming adjustments. (SU8)

[I was mostly nervous because I knew it would take time for me to adjust.] (SU8)

Nabigla po ako dahil 'di pa po ready 'yung sarili ko sa face-to-face po. (SA9)

[I was shocked because I was not ready for face-to-face classes.] (SA9)

Syempre medyo kinakabahan [kasi] malaking adjustment na naman 'yung mangyayari. (SA12)

[Of course, I was slightly nervous because of the adjustment that I need to undergo.] (SA12)

The statements collectively show how students are apprehensive about the challenges of transitioning to the traditional classroom setup after years of learning online. It is assumed by learners that the quality and quantity of workload may differ depending on the learning modality, which is also influenced by their approaches to learning. Besides the perception of students on the difficulty of the tasks to be done in in-person classes, associated with is the lack of psychological readiness due to being held back by their experiences while learning online. This implies that just as how students were able to create their own routines to get through online learning, it is just as important to focus on building comfort in the midst of the overwhelming transition to face-to-face classes. The involvement of open communication for the concerns of students creates a safe space—a smooth bridge between the two learning modes.

Based on the analysis, the re-implementation of in-person classes received reluctance from students as they grew accustomed to learning remotely and perceived that there were adjustments they had to make to adapt to the learning modality. The adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have forced the transition from traditional in-person classes to online classes (Borres et al., 2023). As a result, students have spent almost two years studying within the comfort of their homes. Grade 7 and grade 8 learners were found to be unaccustomed to the transition as they enter a new learning modality after two years of independent learning (Borres et al., 2023). This was supported by Shean (2021) as they drew a conclusion that some students feel like there is a gap between them and a new learning environment.

Learning Challenges During the Resumption of In-person Classes

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic forced the Philippine educational system to transition from traditional in-person classes to distance learning. As a result, students have spent approximately two years studying within the comfort of their home. Hence it is foreseeable that students may face challenges as the in-person classes are being reimplemented.

Difficulty in Meeting the Demands of Face-to-face Classes

Students are having difficulty with their time-management due to the number of tasks that they need to accomplish for school. As quoted by participants:

Challenges ko siguro talaga yung sa oras, the time management. May puyat pa for assignments so, napakalaki talagang challenge sa'kin ngayon na nagbalik yung face-to-face. Medyo wala akong oras para magpahinga... (SA12)

[For me, time management was really my problem. I stay up late to finish my assignments so it is really difficult for me to adapt to face-to-face classes again. I barely have time to rest.] (SA12)

The respondent emphasized the challenges of managing the time at school for classroom-related activities and at home for take-home assignments. With the 8–10 hours spent inside the classroom, the routines of learners have to be adjusted accordingly as in-person classes require adapting to the fixed schedule rather than being flexible like in online classes. They may feel the evident change in the response of their minds and bodies as they focus on double the amount of work they were doing during online learning. Aligned with this impression is the raised matter on sleep deprivation due to late-night study sessions, which leads to the focus on strategies for

completing requirements within a reasonable time while promoting healthy sleeping habits among learners.

Based on the analysis, students perceive the number of school tasks to be a contributing factor as to why they are having difficulty in managing their time. This is in accordance with the findings of Perante et al. (2021) which they have found students having difficulty complying due to their workload and submission. Furthermore, due to their workload, they often experienced a lack of rest. According to Bermundo et al. (2019), sleep deprivation is a circumstance where an individual has a lack of sleep which affects an individual and makes them moodier. Hence, the lack of sleep may further be a factor that affects the learning attitudes of students.

Moreover, students are having difficulty in adjusting to the new learning setup. As quoted below:

Mayroon pa rin pong mga performance task katulad po sa school, unlike sa dati, sa bahay, pwede ka pang tulungan ng kapatid mo... (SU7)

[There are still performance tasks but, unlike before, I can do it at home where my sibling can help me.] (SU7)

Based on the analysis, it implies that students during distance learning received a helping hand from their family members to accomplish their school tasks. Related to the flexibility in time offered by online classes, students also perceive the tasks of online learning to be more workable as they are able to seek direct guidance from elders, mentors, and experts. This implies that students experience an increased access to support and other resources, unlike in a classroom setting where only the teacher/s can assist them. This analysis is in relation to Hoerunisa et al., (2022) that have found students to be more comfortable and convenient studying at home than in a classroom since it gives them more freedom.

Exhaustion

In addition, the theme exhaustion emphasized the different aspects of health of the students that have been negatively affected since the full in-person classes were implemented. Supporting quoted statements are presented below:

I think... pinaka-challenge talaga is yung physical exhaustion... (SU8)

[I think the main challenge is physical exhaustion...] (SU8)

I think, more challenging din siya in terms of mental and emotional health... [I think it is more challenging in terms of mental and emotional health...] (SU8)

Students are unaccustomed to in-person classes due to the differences between in-person classes and online classes, such as school hours, workloads, academic pressure, etc. which challenged the students' adaptability. Their ability to adjust back to the traditional in-person classes are adequate but not outstanding, which results in the physical, emotional and mental burnouts that they have experienced. Students' health should be prioritized by schools since it helps improve their academic performance.

According to Babbar and Gupta (2021), unpreparedness and poor planning of education organizations were evident. Thus, Copeland et al. (2021) stated that it affected students' attention and emotional expression. Moreover, Bermundo et al. (2019) also emphasized that the resumption of in-person classes caused lack of sleep that affects their mood and learning ability.

Coping Mechanisms During the Resumption of In-person Classes

Having coping mechanisms is a very important instrument to regulate emotions and feelings. Thus, this study aimed to evaluate the coping mechanisms developed by students from the two laboratory high schools in the Philippines during the transition to full face-to-face classes. Due to the fact that the Philippines conducted emergency online learning modality from March of 2020 until the recent year, students have encountered challenges throughout the transition from the traditional face-to-face learning modality to emergency online modality to blended learning modality to full face-to-face learning modality. These challenges have caused them to develop coping mechanisms, whether good for their health or not.

Adaptive

Adaptive coping mechanisms, focuses on the positive coping mechanisms developed by students with respect to the challenges they faced during the transition to full face-to-face classes. The respondents had the following statements:

Siguro ang naging coping mechanism ko, makinig sa music tsaka magbasa ng libro. (SU12)

[Personally, I think that listening to music and reading books became my coping mechanism.] (SU12)

Participants said that listening to music and reading books have helped them cope with the sudden changes of the learning modality that they faced. This respondent situated their coping mechanism in the category of enjoyable activities where these are beneficial in relaxation and boosting one's mood. Similarly, according to Negi et al. (2019), students deal with typical stresses through coping techniques such as watching movies, listening to music, reading books, and doing yoga and meditation. It is learned from the interview that listening to music and reading books help the participants regulate their stress level from doing tasks.

Ngayon po... group study po na [face-to-face] mas effective. (SU10)

[Now, face-to-face group studies are more effective.] (SU10)

Through the interview conducted, it is discovered that the participants prefer the full face-to-face learning modality as it is more effective and interactive. One of the styles of learning by two or more people is the mentor-mentee type, where the presence of teachers are acknowledged to guide students to learn the lessons that are being discussed. During the online learning modality, the students experienced only being given a module to study and tasks to answer, without online synchronous classes to have an interaction between students and teachers, leaving no room for questions about the lessons or topics that are given to the students. Another technique used by students is through a group study with fellow students, just like what was said in the aforementioned statement. Group studies allows an enhanced engagement among peers, improving communication, focus, and understanding of what is being studied. With the created opportunity for collaboration, effective study habits can be imposed among students and encouragement can be expanded from one to another. Unlike in a traditional classroom setting, the lack of social interactivity in the online set-up is evident (Bali & Liu, 2018). Learners are generally favorable to in-person classes (Borres et al., 2023). Further, teachers' performances and service also highly affect learners' readiness as they shape the learners' attitudes (Olleras et al., 2022).

Yung mga tao sa paligid mo. Kasi if you surround yourself with good people, talagang kahit na hindi ka okay, makakalimutan mo lahat ng problems mo. (SU12)

[The people around you. Because if you surround yourself with good people, even though you are not okay, you'll forget all your problems.] (SU12)

Another factor of student's perception about the full face-to-face learning modality is the people that surround them. Being surrounded with peers gives a deeper connection between students who are in the same age group. Social support from what one considers as "good people" can act as a buffer against negative emotions. The positive influences of the people surrounding an individual uplifts mood and allows a shared experience that decreases the overwhelming feeling. Being only one piece of the puzzle in dealing with problems, the emotional validation and support given by good relationships can help an individual be equipped to cope with challenges, especially in work. Social support is highlighted as a coping mechanism during times of difficulties (Saltzman et al., 2020). Though some people like the silence and serenity of being alone, other people recognize the need to have good people around them to be their support system when needed.

Siyempre yung future endeavors ko...next year I will go to pursue my course na. [Of course, my future endeavors since I'll already pursue my course next year.]

Education talaga is mahalaga for me because I'm not privileged to waste my time for nothing because I think education is the most practical way para sa'kin, para maabot ko yung mga pangarap ko. (SA12)

[Education is really important for me because I'm not privileged to waste my time for nothing because I think education is the most practical way for me to reach my dreams.] (SA12)

Education on its own is a very important aspect of life. Some people hold on to it like it is their only way of getting a good life. One of the respondents hold on to their trait of being future-oriented in order to pass through the challenges they are facing as students. As they have mentioned the importance of time, they stressed on the act of focusing on their studies in the present as a motivation in paving the path towards their dream. This basically emphasizes the importance of valuing education, and being wise in seeking support and resources, which can eventually lead to identifying one's determination in reaching their dreams. The foundation of all education lies in the visualization of future possibilities, and through the educational process, new images of the future are generated (Holfelder, 2019). The practicality that comes with education is also a way of coping with the sudden changes in learning modalities.

Not everyone is privileged enough to stop studying because of academic burnouts. Thus, the future endeavors of students serve as a motivation and a coping mechanism for students to not stop learning despite the confusing changes that are happening with the Philippine's learning system.

Maladaptive

Moreover, the maladaptive sub theme focuses on the negative coping mechanisms the students developed based on the challenges they faced throughout the transition to full face-to-face classes. Participants responded with the statements:

Emotional eating po. (SA10)

One respondent acknowledges emotional eating as a habit they engage in to cope with emotions, especially with the challenges brought by learning in person. This is caused by the body's stress response, in which fulfilling the cravings for caloric and sugary foods may provide a temporary comfort and pleasure to an individual. So, emotional eating can be a way to temporarily escape from the negative feelings associated with learning difficulties. However, the underlying challenge of binge-eating is weight gain and associated health problems that may surface in the long run. Food is consumed in reaction to negative emotions (Kontinen, 2020). It is also found out in the study of Chamberlin et al. (2019) that individuals with high GPA scores have high scores in emotional eating. It is implied here that students that maintain high grades through exerting much effort to their school work have high stress levels and use food to deal with the pressure of earning and maintaining their grade.

I think social media. Lagi akong...tuwing nagvi-view ako ng work...kapag na-overwhelm po ako talaga is nags-scroll lang ako...Naging coping mechanism ko siya kapag masyadong maraming workload. (SA10)

[I think social media. Whenever I view the work, I need to do and I get overwhelmed, I just scroll through social media. It became my coping mechanism whenever there is too much workload.] (SA10)

Social media serves as a way to distract students from the negative emotions imposed by face-to-face learning. With the experienced difficulties in the workload, the associated overwhelming feeling pushes an individual to create an “escape plan” as an emotional response to stress, resorting to social media. Although it can provide relaxation and entertainment, social media has its drawbacks. It can stir up more procrastination for the student as spending time on social media may delay the time in completing school work, and eventually increase stress. In the study of Chen & Xiao (2022), it was implied that there is a positive correlation between social media use and negative emotions, as induced by the distorted perception of individuals on what is being portrayed in social media. According to Kgarose & Ramoshaba (2022), some students utilized unhealthy coping mechanisms. Overwhelming feelings occur when dealing with something big. Although too much workload is considered normal with how often it occurs, dealing with it is always a burden to the mental and emotional health of students. Little breaks in between studying is a good habit to reset and rest the mind for a few minutes before going back to studying and learning.

In general, the individual coping mechanisms of students vary due to the differences in the challenges and experiences they faced (Chowdhury, 2019). Most of them have developed adaptive coping mechanisms, while some developed maladaptive coping mechanisms. Furthermore, some students haven't fully coped yet to the present situation regarding the continuation of full face-to-face classes while some of them have accepted the changes.

Conclusions

The reimplementation of face-to-face classes resulted in varying learning attitudes of laboratory school learners. Two main themes emerged upon analyzing their responses: excitement and unfamiliarity. Excitement emerged from the possibility of social interaction, while unfamiliarity resulted from the adjustments required to meet their class objectives.

The sudden change in learning modality presented challenges, such as difficulty meeting the demands of face-to-face classes and exhaustion. Transitioning to a physical learning environment took learners out of the comfort of their homes, increasing their responsibilities as both children and students. This heightened their responsibilities and led to physical, emotional, and mental burnout due to the effort required to adapt to the new learning environment.

As students continue to adjust, they have adopted various coping mechanisms to ease the transition. Both adaptive and maladaptive coping strategies were observed. Developmental activities and forms of entertainment helped some students manage the transition. However, others struggled with adaptation, resorting to uncontrollable approaches that could further negatively impact their well-being.

Transitioning to full in-person classes requires laboratory school learners to instill habits in order to effectively adapt to a new learning environment. Findings of the study were able to meet the objectives in determining the learning attitudes of learners towards face-to-face classes. In this manner, future implications of the current study are identified which can bridge gaps in face-to-face education. Particularly, educational institutions may now implement policies on providing students with comprehensive academic and psychological support initiatives, including tutoring and counseling programs, to ensure a competent and sustainable learning system. In addition, academic institutions may also offer professional development for teachers and instructors to equip them with skills and knowledge to recognize and understand the needs and struggles of students experiencing academic stress.

References

- Adnan, M., & Anwar, K. (2020). Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Students' perspectives. *Journal of Pedagogical Sociology and Psychology*, 1(2), 45-51. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPSP.2020261309>
- Aleksieva, L., Yovkova, B., & Peytcheva-Forsyth, R. (2018, December). Factors affecting students' attitudes towards online learning - The case of Sofia University [Paper presentation]. *Proceedings of the 44th International Conference on Applications of Mathematics in Engineering and Economics: (AMEE'18)*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5082043>
- Andal, M.S., Trabucon, K.C. D., Camarao, Z.A.M., Candatu, V.R., Gajo, L.M.P., Jao, A.J.B., Lim, K.N.B., Munder, A.T., Nicol, L.D., Santiago, C.D., & Ecalne, J.K.T. (2022). A comparative study on the perspectives of CEU-manila SOP community on flexible and face-to-face learning modalities: Pharmacy Education in the New Normal. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*, 12(1),5–14. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2022.12.1.0173>
- Applebaum, A., Finlayson, C. S., Fu, M. R., Squires, A., Van Cleave, J., O'Cearbhaill, R., & DeRosa, A. P. (2019). The experience of being aware of disease status in women with recurrent ovarian cancer: A phenomenological study. *Journal of Palliative Medicine*, 22(4), 377-384. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jpm.2018.0127>
- Asarta, C. J., & Schmidt, J. R. (2020). The effects of online and blended experience on outcomes in a blended learning environment. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 44, 100708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2019.100708>

- Babbar, M. & Gupta, T. (2021). Response of educational institutions to COVID-19 pandemic: An inter-country comparison. *Policy Features in Education*, 20(4), 469-491. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14782103211021937>
- Bali, S., & Liu, M. C. (2018). Students' perceptions toward online learning and face-to-face learning courses. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1108(1), 012094. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1108/1/012094>
- Baloran, E. T. (2020). Knowledge, attitudes, anxiety, and coping strategies of students during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Loss and Trauma*, 25(8), 635-642. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325024.2020.1769300>
- Bermundo, M., Frias, A., Manong, C., Mate, A., & Mendiola, C. (2019, March 16). Effects of sleep deprivation to the mental health stability of selected grade 9 students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) high school (RMCHS). *Academia.edu - Share research*. https://www.academia.edu/44918963/Effects_of_Sleep_Deprivation_to_the_Mental_Health_Stability_of_Selected_Grade_9_Students_of_Ramon_Magsaysay_Cubao_High_School_RMCHS
- Birbal, D. R., Ramdass, D. M., & Harripaul, M. C. (2018). Student teachers' attitudes towards blended learning. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.15640/jehd.v7n2a2>
- Bordeos, M. L., Lagman, K. R., & Sta Cruz, I. P. (2022). Students in the new normal: their experiences in the pandemic's limited face-to-face classes. *American Journal of Education and Technology*, 1(3), 42-51. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajet.v1i3.979>
- Borres, C. J., Mccary, M. C., & Potane, J. D. (2023). Students' readiness for the face-to-face classes in junior and senior high school. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 11(1), 389-400. <https://doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/16028>
- Camacho, A., Correia, N., Daniel, J.R., & Zaccoletti, S. (2021). Anxiety and social support as predictors of student academic motivation during the COVID-19. *Frontier Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.644338>
- Chamberlin, A., Nguyen-Rodriguez, S., Gray, V. B., Reiboldt, W., Peterson, C., & Spruijt-Metz, D. (2018). Academic-related factors and emotional eating in adolescents. *Journal of School Health*, 88(7), 493-449. <https://doi.org/10.1111%2Fjosh.12638>
- Cimene, F. T., Du, E. C., Alonsabe, O. C., Kurangking, J. A., Santander, M. E., Alvarez, B. G., Amper, D. A., Carbonero, L., Cosain, S. N., Cotongan, S. A., Gumana, S. T., Omar, S., Han-awon, M., Labadan, M., Gaso-Maandig, T. A., Menil, T., Mohammad Exan, I., Romasanta, T., Sanggacala, N., ... Gomez, R. (2023). Navigating the educational landscape: Philosophy, trends, and issues in the Philippines. *Beyond Books Publication*.
- Chen, M., & Xiao, X. (2022). The effect of social media on the development of students' affective variables. *Frontiers in Psychology*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1010766>
- Chowdhury, M. R. (2019, September 3). What is coping theory? Definition & worksheets. *PositivePsychology.com*. <https://positivepsychology.com/coping-theory/>
- Copeland, W. E., McGinnis, E., Bai, Y., Adams, Z., Nardone, H., Devadanam, V., Rettew, J., & Hudziak, J. J. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on college student mental health and wellness. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 60(1), 134-141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2020.08.466>
- Del Rosario, L. S., Barrot, J. S., & Llenares, I. I. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 7321-7338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x>
- Fleetwood, D. (2022, August 8). Judgmental sampling: Definition, examples and advantages. *QuestionPro*. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/judgmental-sampling/>
- George, A. A. (2021, November 23). Attitude: Content, structure, function. *ClearIAS*. <https://www.clearias.com/attitude/>
- Gherheș, V., Stoian, C. E., Fărcașiu, M. A., & Stanici, M. (2021). E-learning vs. face-to-face learning: Analyzing students' preferences and behaviors. *Sustainability*, 13(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084381>
- Heotis, E. (2020). Phenomenological research methods: extensions of Husserl and Heidegger. *International Journal of School and Cognitive Psychology*, 7(2), <https://doi.org/10.35248/2469-9837.19.6.221>
- Hoerunisa, N., Nurisfah, A., Tabroni, I., & Rini, F. H. (2022). Learning during the Covid-19 pandemic: proceeding student learning interests and the continuity of face-to-face learning. *Kampret Journal*, 2(1), 42-49. <https://doi.org/10.35335/kampret.v2i1.102>
- Holfelder, A. K. (2019). Towards a sustainable future with education? *Sustainability Science*, 14, 943-952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00682-z>
- Hood, J., Chen, Y., Jacques, L., & Herbert, D. (2022). Perceptions of students and faculty on the various delivery methods of instruction. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 10(4), 245-252. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-10-4-13>

- Hurst, B., Wallace, R., & Nixon, S. B. (2013). The impact of social interaction on student learning. *Reading Horizons: A Journal of Literacy and Language Arts*, 52(4).
- Juanis, A. A., & Ejus, G. A. (2020). Students' perspective on online learning in Politeknik Kota Kinabalu. *Jurnal Pengajian Umum*, 50-56. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14916.35205>
- Karaaslan, H., & Kılıç, N. (2019). Students' attitudes towards blended language courses: A case study. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 15(1), 174-199. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.547699>
- Kgarose, M. F., & Ramoshaba, D. J. (2022). Analysing coping strategies of students for online teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478), 11(9), 343-347. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v11i9.2192>
- Kontinen, H. (2020). Emotional eating and obesity in adults: The role of depression, sleep and genes. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 79(3), 283-289. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0029665120000166>
- Landscape. (n.d.). Cambridge Dictionary | English Dictionary, Translations & Thesaurus. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/learner-english/landscape>
- Mather, M., & Sarkans, A. (2018). Student perceptions of online and face-to-face learning. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 10(2) 61-76.
- Negi, A. S., Khanna, A., & Aggarwal, R. (2019). Psychological health, stressors and coping mechanism of engineering students. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 24(4), 511-520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2019.1570856>
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). Face-to-face, online and hybrid education: university students' opinions and preferences. *Journal of Digital Educational Technology*, 2(2), 2206. <https://doi.org/10.30935/jdet/12384>
- Nora, A., & Crisp, G. (2007). *Journal of College Retention: Research, Theory, and Practice*, 9(3), 337-356. <https://doi.org/10.2190/CS.9.3.e>
- Nuangchalerm, P., Thongbunma, J., & Supakam, S. (2021). Secondary teachers and students' perspectives towards online learning amid the COVID-19 outbreak. *Gagasan Pendidikan Indonesia*, 2, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.30870/gpi.v2i1.10524>.
- Olleras, J. L., Dagwayan, M., Dejacto, A. M., Mangay, J. R., Ebarsabal, M., Diaz, D. J., & Minyamin, A. (2022). The life of the laters: students procrastination in accomplishing academic deadlines in online learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(5), 444-454. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6791776>
- Ondicho, T. (2021). Students' perspectives on online learning at the University of Nairobi during the COVID-19. In *Youths in struggles: Unemployment, politics, and cultures in contemporary Africa* (pp. 233-250). Research Institute of Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa Tokyo University of Foreign Studies.
- Ora, A., Sahatcija, R., & Ferhataj, A. (2018). Learning styles and the hybrid learning: An empirical study about the impact of learning styles on the perception of the hybrid learning. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1), 138-148. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mjss-2018-001>
- O'Regan, D., Jackson, M. L., Young, A. H., & Rosenzweig, I. (2021). Understanding the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, lockdowns and social isolation on sleep quality. *Nature and Science of Sleep*, 13, 2053-2064. <https://doi.org/10.2147/nss.s266240>
- Paul, J., & Jefferson, F. (2019). A comparative analysis of student performance in an online vs. face-to-face environmental science course from 2009 to 2016. *Frontiers in Computer Science*. 1(7). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomp.2019.00007>
- Perante, L., Solmiano, E. M., Lunesto, J. P., Tus, J., Malicdem, J., & Malaca, J. (2021). A phenomenological study on the lived experiences of students on blended learning amidst COVID-19. *International Journal Of Advanced Research and Innovative Ideas In Education*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13717864.v1>.
- Philippine News Agency. (2022, February 28). IATF approves amended guidelines for Alert Level 1. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1168637>
- Ranjbar, K., Hosseinpour, H., Shahriarirad, R., Ghaem, H., Jafari, K., Rahimi, T., Mirahmadizadeh, A., & Hosseinpour, P. (2021). Students' attitude and sleep pattern during school closure following COVID-19 pandemic quarantine: a web-based survey in south of Iran. *Environmental Health and Preventive Medicine*, 26(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-021-00950-4>
- Ransom, A., LaGrant, B., Spiteri, A., Kushnir, T., Anderson, A. K., De Rosa, E. (2022). Face-to-face learning enhances the social transmission of information. *Public Library of Science One*, 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264250>
- Saltzman, L. Y., Hansel, T. C., & Bordnick, P. S. (2020). Loneliness, isolation, and social support factors in post-COVID-19 mental health. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 12(S1), S55-S57. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000703>

Sanpanich, N. (2021). Investigating factors affecting students' attitudes toward hybrid learning. *rEFLections*, 28(2), 208-227. <https://doi.org/10.61508/refl.v28i2.253093>

Shaheen, M., Pradhan, S., & Ranajee. (2019). Sampling in Qualitative Research. In M. Gupta, M. Shaheen, & K. Reddy (Eds.), *Qualitative Techniques for Workplace Data Analysis* (pp. 25-51). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5366-3.ch002>

Shean, M. (2021, January 17). Is your child anxious about starting school for the first time? Here's how you can help. *The Conversation*. <https://theconversation.com/is-your-child-anxious-about-starting-school-for-the-first-time-heres-how-you-can-help>

Villar, M. C. G., Filipinas, J. P., Villanueva, J. B., & Cabello, C. A. (2022). The transition, transformation, and adaptation from modular-printed instruction to limited face-to-face classes: a phenomenology. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7162077>

Villarama, J. A., Santos, J. P. E., Adsuara, J. P. Antalan, J. A. A. R., & Gundran, J. F. (2022). What's on your mind? Impact of online education on students' mental wellness. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 9(4), 240-248. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v9i4.4243>

Wirhana, L., Welch, A., Williamson, M., Christensen, M., Bakon, S., & Craft, J. (2018). Using Colaizzi's method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), 30-34. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e151>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Princess Stephanie B. Rayray

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Cassandra Alexa T. Bagarra

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Sandra Camille C. Bermudez

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Markko Enzo S. Galvez

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Ma. Ydane G. Javier

Central Luzon State University – Philippines

Joseph A. Villarama

Central Luzon State University – Philippines